

XORIJIY TIL – INGLIZ TILI TA'LIMINI ZARURATI MASALASI

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani

2 son kasb hunar maktabi

ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishning zarurati, qoidalar, ikkinchi til sifatida xususiyati, ingliz tilini o'rganishning onson yo'llari haqida tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tili, ikkinchi til, maqsad, mohiyat, ma'naviyat

Аннотация: В статье даны рекомендации о необходимости преподавания английского языка, его правилах, его природе как второго языка, а также простых способах изучения английского языка.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, второй язык, цель, сущность, духовность.

Abstract: The article provides recommendations on the need to teach English, its rules, its nature as a second language, as well as simple ways to learn English.

Key words: English, second language, purpose, essence, spirituality.

Xorijiy til ta'limida “kompetensiya”, “lingvistik kompetensiya” tushunchalarining mazmuni hamda mohiyatini zamonaviy jamiyatda ta'limni zamonaviy tendensiyalari, maqsad hamda vazifalari bilan bog'lash zarurati tug'iladi. Ma'lumki, bugungi kunda axborot olish jarayonida intellektni milliy boylik sifatida, insonning ma'naviy qarashlari, uning har tomonlama rivojlanganligi, professional tayyorgarlik doirasining kengligi, ijodga intilish bilan birga nostandart vazifalarni hal qila olish qobiliyati muhim omillaridan biri sifatida baholanadi. Kommunikativ kompetensiyaga berilgan ta'riflar juda ko'p bo'lishiga

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qaramay biz L.T.Ahmedova, Ye.A.Lagaylarning fikriga qo'shilamiz. Zero, “kommunikativ kompetensiya – til sohibi bilan chet tilda muloqot qilishni amalga oshirish uchun tayyor bo'lishlik hamda maktab o'quvchilarining tili o'rganilayotgan mamlakatning tili va madaniyatini yaxshi anglagan holda o'zining davlatini ham muloqot jarayonida tanishtira olish qobiliyatidir”

Tadqiqotchilar tomonidan kommunikativ kompetensiyani tashkil etuvchi komponentlar ham turlicha talqin etilgan. L.T.Ahmedova, Ye.A.Lagaylar kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni lingvistik, sosiolingvistik (sosiomadaniy), pragmatik (diskursiv) komponentlarga ajratadilar²¹. J.Jalolov, G.Mahkamova va SH.Ashurovlar SEFRning oltita darajasi bo'yicha xorijiy tilni o'qitishda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning, (domestic model) komponentlarini lingvistik kompetensiya (til va nutq birliklari va ularning ishlatish qoidalari), sosiolingvistik kompetensiya (sosiomadaniy, disskursda tildan foydalanish), pragmatik kompetensiya (ijtimoiy, diskurs, strategik va sosiomadaniy) kabi turlarga bo'ladi.

A.T.Irisqulov kommunikativ kompetensiya quyidagilarni qamrab olishini ta'kidlaydi: 1) tilga oid materialni chuqur o'zlashtirganlik; 2) ijtimoiy-lingvistik yoki sosiolingvistik omilkorlik; 3) maqsadga yo'naltirgan omilkorliko'ziga xos tuzilishga egaligiga urg'u beradi.

Olim lingvistik kompetensiyani shakllantirishni o'rganish davomida “leksik birliklar, grammatik konstruksiyalar, chet tilining fonetik me'yorlari, shuningdek ma'nosida madaniy komponentga ega bo'lgan leksik birliklar va ularni ongli ravishda qabul qilish, og'zaki va reseptiv tarzda samarali qo'llash ko'nikmalarini o'z ichiga olgan murakkab ta'lim” , – deb ta'kidlaydi. Xususan, M.X.Gulyamova: “Kommunikativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishda avvalo lingvistik kompetensiya, ya'ni fonetik, leksik va grammatik bilimlarni bilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi”, – deb ta'kidlagan holda “Fonetika orqali tovushlarni to'g'ri talaffuz qilish, urg'uni to'g'ri qo'yish va intonasiyalar o'rganilsa, leksika orqali so'zlar, so'z birikmalari, idiomalar o'rganiladi”, – deb yozadi”.

SHuni ta'kidlash kerakki, metodist olimlar “Lingvistik kompetensiya kommunikativ kompetensiyaning asosiy tarkibiy qismi sifatida” talqin etishadi. R.YU. Barsuk yozishicha lingvistik kompetensiya “tilning leksik, grammatik, fonetik qonunlariga egalik qilish, gapirish va matni tuzish uchun (vaziyatga mos keladigan) tanlash hamda aloqa qonunlari, kommunikativ tamoyillari va mezonlari, suhbat strategiyasi va taktikasi, nutq va kommunikativ harakatlarning moslashuvchan tizimi, nutqdan foydalanishning ijtimoiy me'yorlari aloqa sohasi darajasida ishlaydi” .

Lingvistik kompetensiyani tanlash qoidalari mavjud. Lingvistik kompetensiya o'zlashtirilgan lisoniy belgilar va ularni birlashtirish qoidalari yordamida cheklanmagan miqdorda lisoniy jihatdan to'g'ri gaplarni tushunish va ayta olish qobiliyati sifatida ta'riflanadi. I.A. Zimnyaya lingvistik kompetensiyani: “..til tizimi va uning chet tilidagi muloqot sharoitlarida ishlash qoidalarini bilish deb, ya'ni lingvistik kompetensiyani ma'lum kommunikativ salohiyatga ega lingvistik vositalarning mavjudligini, til vositalari va ularning funktsiya, vazifalarini bilish” sifatida qaraydi . M.Ruzmetova ta'kidlashicha: “Lingvistik kompetensiya nutqiy, til kompetensiyalardan iborat. Nutqiy kompetensiya(speech competence) deganda, nutq faoliyati turlari – tinglab tushunish (listening), gapirish (speaking), o'qish (reading) va yozuv (writing)ni hamda til materialini (fonetika, leksika, grammatika) haqidagi bilimlar bo'yicha ko'nikmalarni egallashni nazarda tutadi.

Olimlarning fikricha til o'rganuvchilarning lingvistik tilning leksik, grammatik, fonetik qonunlariga egalik qilish • aloqa qonunlari, kommunikativ o'zaro ta'sir prinsiplari va qoidalari • gapirish va matni tuzish uchun (vaziyatga mos keladigan) uslubiy tanlash qoidalari • suhbatni o'tkazish strategiyasi va taktikasi, nutq va kommunikativ harakatlarning moslashuvchan tizimi • nutqdan foydalanishning ijtimoiy me'yorlari aloqa sohasi darajasida ishlaydi kompetensiyasi darslik materiallari bo'yicha olgan bilimlari, amaliyot bilan bilimlarni bog'lay olish hamda kommunikasiyaga erisha olish malakasidir.

Lingvistik kompetensiya negizida berilgan bilim va malakalar og'zaki va yozma nutqni rivojlantirishga qaratilishi maqsadga muvofiqdir. L.Axmedova lingvistik kompetensiyani “lisoniy material (fonetika, so'z boyligi, grammatikasi)ni bilish va o'rganilayotgan til madaniyatining vakillari bilan muloqot qilish uchun yetarli darajada nutqiy faoliyat turlariga (tinglash, gapirish, o'qish, yozish) ega bo'lishni nazarda tutadi deb tasniflaydi. Anglashiladiki, bunda zarur so'z boyligi, og'zaki ifoda va idiomalarni o'zlashtirmasdan, leksikadagi konnotativ ma'nolarni anglamasdan, grammatika, intonasiya va idiomalarni o'zlashtirmasdan turib lisoniy kompetensiyaning talab etilgan darajasiga erishish mumkin emas.

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